

INFLUENCE OF CONDITIONS ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF BEAN VARIETIES GROWN AS A REPEAT CROP

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Abstract. *In the given article, the indicators of yield and crop-producing power of bean varieties grown in normal and arid conditions on typical gray soils of Samarkand region are studied and the features of drought resistance are analyzed. This article presents research on the selection, analysis and allocation of drought-resistant varieties of beans as repeat crops grown on the areas of typical gray soils freed from grain crops, as well as on the allocation and introduction into production of productive varieties suitable for this area.*

Keywords: *Samarkand region, bean, a repeat crop, legumes, yield, crop-producing power.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that large-scale scientific research on the cultivation of leguminous crops, especially beans, is being conducted worldwide. According to many data, the importance of repeated sowing in increasing soil fertility and productivity is great, since grain crops, when planted in repeated sowings, are good predecessors for crops that are planted after them, as well as for obtaining high-quality grain [1].

Definitely, drought is the main physiological limitation of crop yield and productivity, especially beans.[4] Drought has a significant impact on the growth and development of repeated crops. It is also expected that global warming will lead to a decrease in soil moisture due to increased evaporation, thereby suppressing plant growth. As a result of climate change, there is a decrease in precipitation and water shortage, in such conditions, the selection and introduction of drought-resistant plants into production is of great economic importance [6].

It is known to everyone that water shortage is the main limiting factor in crop production worldwide.[5] To improve the plant resistance to drought, it is necessary to have knowledge of the genetics and physiology of tolerance mechanisms in the selection and development of important varieties. Productivity is the main selection parameter used in drought conditions [7]. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2019 N. 259 "On the rational placement of agricultural crops and projected production volumes of the 2019 harvest" was adopted. According to this decision, it is planned to sow 824,350 hectares or 75.5% of 1,091,630 hectares of the main crop - winter wheat, of which about 284,067 hectares will be sown with legumes [8]. At present time, according to the statistical agency on bean cultivation in all farms, the leading positions in bean cultivation in all categories of farms are occupied by Samarkand, Namangan, Fergana, Bukhara and Andijan. The following places are occupied by Sirdarya, Tashkent, Jizzakh and Karakalpakstan regions [3]. It is known that the yield and productivity indicators of agricultural crops are determined by the quantity and quality of the harvested elements. The grain yield of bean varieties planted in areas cleared of grain as a secondary crop depends on the elements of the crop formed in the plant, the number of pods, the quantity and quality of grains. Because with repeated planting of bean varieties in normal and dry conditions, the influence of physiological processes during the formation of grains in legumes is

strong, as a result, some of the grains are fully formed, and some remain immature. Therefore, when growing beans as a secondary crop in normal and dry conditions, the formation of pods, the number of pods, the weight of pods, the number of grains in pods, and the weight of 1000 grains were studied.

Materials and methods. The experiments were conducted in typical sideroses conditions of Nakhangov Sherbek state farm in Pstdargom district of Samarkand region. The following bean varieties were used for the experiment as a repeat crop on weed-free fields: Ravat, Mahsuldor and Oltin Soch. The soil of the experimental field was non-saline, the 30 cm deep soil layer. During the scientific research, biometric measurements and phenological observations were carried out based on the Methodology for Conducting Field Experiments (UzPITI, 2007). The climate of the region is continental, with strong solar radiation, daily and seasonal changes, a long hot and dry summer season and slightly cold winter. Today, the temperature in such regions is relatively high, as a result of which drought threatens the growth and development of plants, the cultivation of drought- and heat-resistant plants in such regions and their effective collection are of great national economic importance [1].

Results and discussion. Our scientific research was conducted in the form of field experiments. Our research was conducted under two different conditions: under conditions of sufficient moisture LFMC (limited field moisture capacity) - 70% and under arid conditions LFMC - 50%. During the study, the yield and productivity indicators of bean varieties were studied at the stages of development under conditions of sufficient moisture and under arid conditions. The results obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Productivity indicators of bean varieties for 2022-2023

No	Variety	Stem height (cm)	Number of productive branches in 1 bush (pieces)	Number of pods in 1 bush (pieces)	Pod length (cm)	Number of grains in pod (pieces)	Weight of grains in 1 pod (g)	Weight of 1000 grains (g)
CHDNS -70 %								
1	Ravat	55,46	13,76	38,27	10,24	4,82	3,91	643,28
2	Mahsuldor	60,33	14,87	40,71	11,87	5,73	4,74	796,33
3	Oltin soch	58,18	12,25	35,43	9,83	4,12	3,06	503,81
Dry CHDNS -50 %								
1	Ravat	49,53	10,17	25,03	6,19	4,01	2,88	438,64
2	Mahsuldor	47,14	12,63	31,26	7,61	4,93	3,69	687,49
3	Oltin soch	48,76	8,67	22,78	5,73	3,58	2,03	341,27

At the time of analyzing, the productivity indicators of our experiment under conditions of LFMC -70%, the average height of bean varieties is from 55.46 cm to 60.33 cm, when analyzing in dry conditions, the average height of plants is from 47.14 cm up to 49.53 cm. It was found that under the influence of humidity, the height of plants decreased from 5.93 cm to 13.19 cm. It was

found that the number of productive branches in bean varieties with sufficient moisture is from 12.25 to 14.87, the number of productive branches is less than the ratio in the variety "Oltin soch" up to 12.25 and a higher result in the variety "Oltin soch". The variety "Mahsuldor" is noted up to 14.87. In dry conditions, it was found that the number of productive branches in bean varieties is in the range of 8.67-12.63 pcs., the smallest number of productive branches is 8.67 pcs. for the variety "Oltin soch" and the highest result - 12 for the variety "Mahsuldor". It was determined that there are 63 units.

Definitely, when analyzing bean varieties by the length of the pods, the variety "Mahsuldor" with sufficient moisture had longer pods of 11.87 cm in length, the variety "Oltin soch" had relatively short pods of 9.83 cm in length, and long pods were observed in dry conditions. It was found that the variety "Mahsuldor" had 7.61 cm, and the variety "Oltin soch" - 5.73 cm. It was found that the length of the pods of the variety "Oltin soch" is shorter than other varieties, even in dry and humid conditions.

The highest result for the number of grains in a pod was noted in the variety "Mahsuldor" - up to 5.73 grains under conditions of sufficient moisture, and the lowest value was noted in the variety "Oltin soch" - up to 4.12 grains. In dry conditions, it was found to be up to 4.93 in the variety "Mahsuldor", and the lowest indicator was up to 3.58 in the variety "Oltin Soch". The variety "Ravat" occupied an intermediate place under sufficient moisture and drought.

Surprisingly, at the time of analyzing the experiments, a high result for the weight of grain per pod was noted in the variety "Mahsuldor" even under conditions of LFMC - 70% and dry LFMC - 50%.

In the experiments, the highest result for the weight of 1000 grains was determined in the variety "Mahsuldor" even with sufficient watering and in dry conditions, and the lowest result was noted in the variety "Oltin Soch".

The weight of 1000 grains of the "Mahsuldor" variety under conditions of sufficient moisture was 796.33 g, and under drought conditions - 687.49 g. The coefficient is lower than that of the "Oltin Soch" variety - 1000 grains under conditions of sufficient moisture, weight - from 503.81 g, under dry conditions 341.27 g. grain yield was obtained.

The "Ravat" variety occupied an intermediate place in terms of grain weight under conditions of sufficient moisture and drought.

It is clear that the productivity indicators of bean varieties in dry conditions are somewhat reduced compared to conditions with sufficient moisture, which is why the growth and development of the plant slows down due to a lack of moisture, especially in the budding and flowering phases. At the end of our study, there was studied the effect of humidity on yield, and the results are presented in Figure 1.

Moisture is one of the limiting factors for plant growth, development and productivity. Drought has a significant effect on plant productivity. It is evident that the "Mahsuldor" bean variety showed high results in both conditions.

Under conditions of 70%, the average grain yield of bean varieties is 19.7-23.8 c/ha, high grain yield - in the variety "Mahsuldor" - 23.8 c/ha, low - in the variety "Oltin soch" - 19.7 c/ha.

Under dry conditions, the average grain yield of the bean variety is 15.5-20.4 c/ha, higher grain yield - in the variety "Mahsuldor" - 20.4 c/ha, lower - in the variety "Oltin soch" - 15.5 c/ha.

Among the bean varieties, it has been established that the "Mahsuldor" variety is resistant to drought, and the variety Oltin soch is resistant to the effects of drought.

Figure 1. Effect of humidity on the yield of bean varieties.

Conclusion. By summarizing it is important to suggest that in the conditions of Samarkand region, it has been established that the yield and productivity indicators of bean varieties planted as a secondary crop in grain-free fields are higher than those of other varieties in conditions of sufficient moisture and arid environment. Based on the mentioned above ideas, high economic efficiency can be achieved if the “Mahsuldor” variety is grown as a secondary crop in grain-free areas, in areas with typical gray soils.

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